

Spectrophotometric Determination of Osmium with 1-Thiocarbamido-3-methylpyrazol-5-one

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1-Thiocarbamido-3-methylpyrazol-5-one has been used as a reagent for spectrophotometric determination of osmium. The reddish yellow colour in the alkaline solution has been measured at 400 m μ . The colour system obeys Beer's law over a wide range of the metal concentrations. Sensitivity is found to be 0.028 γ Os/cm². The composition of the coloured species in solution has also been determined by Job's method and the mole-ratio method.

In an earlier communication¹ we discussed the possibilities of the use of pyrazolone derivatives for the gravimetric and colorimetric estimations of a number of cations and anions. 1-Carbamido-3-methylpyrazol-5-one² was used by us for spectrophotometric determination of osmium. The present communication reports the application of 1-thiocarbamido-3-methylpyrazol-5-one as a reagent for the spectrophotometric determination of osmium. The reagent combines with octavalent osmium to provide a deep reddish yellow colour at the pH range of 6.5-11.0. The colour has maximum absorption at 400 m μ and the system obeys Beer's law to 26 p.p.m. of Os(VIII).

The results obtained by Job's method⁴ of continued variation and the mole-ratio method⁵ suggest that the colour species in solution has the metal-ligand ratio of 1:2.

EXPERIMENTAL

Optical measurements of the coloured solutions were made with a Unicam SP 600 spectrophotometer using glass cells of 1 cm thickness. A Cambridge bench type pH-meter was used for the pH measurements.

Procedure.—A solution of Os(VIII) (250 ml) was prepared by dissolving 1 g. of osmic acid (OsO₄) in 0.02*N*-NaOH solution. A 0.001*M* solution of Os(VIII) was prepared by diluting the above stock solution to a calculated volume. The reagent, 1-thiocarbamido-3-methylpyrazol-5-one, was prepared according to De³. The reagent being sparingly soluble in water, a 1% solution was prepared by dissolving the reagent in 0.02*N*-NaOH solution.

Absorbance.—An aliquot portion of the Os solution was taken in a 25-ml flask and the reagent solution (2 ml) was added to it. The pH of the solution was adjusted to about 10.5 and finally it was diluted to 25 ml with water. The deep reddish yellow colour developed became maximum after 2 hr. A reagent solution was also prepared under

1. Poddar *et al.*, Communicated to *Z. anal. Chem.*, 1964.
2. Poddar and Adhya, *Science & Culture*, 1964, 30, 50.
3. This *Journal*, 1926, 3, 32.
4. *Ann. chim.*, 1928, x, 9, 113.
5. Yoe and Jones, *Ind. Eng. Chem., Anal. Ed.*, 1944, 16, 111.

similar conditions. Optical densities of the solutions were then measured at different wave lengths at an interval of $10\text{ m}\mu$ against the reagent solution as blank. The intensity of absorption was found to increase continuously with the decrease of wave length. But as the reagent itself showed much absorption below $400\text{ m}\mu$, measurements were made at $400\text{ m}\mu$, which was found to be quite suitable.

Effect of pH, Reagent Concentration, and Time.—pHs of the solutions containing a known amount of Os (VIII) and the reagent solution (5 ml) were adjusted to different values. The volume of each solution was made to 25 ml and optical densities were measured at $400\text{ m}\mu$. The optical density values were constant between pH 9.6 and 10.9. Above pH 10.9, the colour of the solution gradually faded, due probably to decomposition. Below pH 6.0, the solution became green with separation of a greenish black precipitate.

The effect of the reagent concentrations on the colour system was studied with a known amount of Os (VIII) solution and different amounts of the reagent solution, maintaining the pH within the optimum range, mentioned above; 2.0 ml of the reagent solution (1%) was found sufficient for the maximum colour with 1.0 ml of 0.001M Os (VIII) solution.

The osmium-reagent colour developed slowly at the room temperature, but at the optimum pH range and with the optimum reagent concentration, the maximum colour developed after 2 hr. at the room temperature (30°). Once developed fully, the intensity of the colour remained unchanged for a period of about 36 hr.

The osmium-reagent colour obeyed Beer's law for a wide range of the metal concentrations (Fig. 1). Spectrophotometric sensitivity (Sandell) of the colour reaction, calculated from Beer's law curve, was found to be $0.028\gamma\text{ Os/cm}^2$.

FIG. 1

Composition of the Complex in Solution.—The composition of the coloured species in solution was studied by Job's method⁴. The absorption of the complementary mixtures of equimolar solutions (0.001M) of Os (VIII) and the reagent (0.001M) in a constant volume of 15 ml, after proper adjustment of pH (10.7 ± 0.1) etc. and dilution to 25 ml, were

measured at 400 m μ . From Fig. 2 it will be seen that the complex species responsible for the colour has a metal-ligand ratio of 1:2.

For the mole-ratio method³, solutions were prepared at pH 10.8 so that the Os (VIII) concentration remained constant, but the ratio of the moles of reagent to the moles of osmium varied from 0.5 to 4.0. The absorbances of these solutions were measured at 400 m μ against a water blank. The curve in Fig. 3 shows a break at the metal-ligand ratio of 1:2.

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Received April 27, 1964.